

Atmospheric Responses to Arctic Sea Ice Loss in a High-top Atmospheric General Circulation Model

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1. Introduction and model description

This study uses Whole Atmosphere Community Climate Model version 6 (WACCM6) with specified chemistry to investigate the atmospheric response to Arctic sea-ice variability. The high-top configuration of WACCM6 allows more realistic representation of stratosphere-troposphere interactions. WACCM6 results are compared with six other AGCM results from the Blue-Action (blueaction.eu) coordinated experiment.

Fig 1. Vertical grid spacing in WACCM6 & CAM6 (courtesy by J. Richter).

2. Experiment design

EXP1	EXP2
Time-varying Arctic SIC	Climatological Arctic SIC
Time-varying Global SST	Time-varying Global SST

- 1979-2014 AMIP-type simulations forced with daily sea-ice concentration (SIC) and sea surface temperature (SST) from Met Office Hadley Centre, with GHG concentration and aerosol given by CMIP6.
- 30 members for each WACCM6 experiment.
- 7 different AGCM ensembles (total 123 members including WACCM6) using the same protocol are compared.

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3. Sea level pressure variability can be decomposed into internal atmospheric variability, SST-forced, & SIC-forced components

Fig 2. Top: DJF sea-level pressure (SLP) variance decomposition for WACCM6. Bottom: ratios to total SLP variability. $\bar{(\)}$ means ensemble average.

Fig 3. Top: SIC-forced SLP variability of seven AGCMs. Bottom: ratios to each AGCM's total SLP variability.

Fig 4. Ratio of SLP variance decomposition to total variability as functions of ensemble size. Each ensemble size is randomly sampled 1000 times (shown as light color shadings).

4. EOF1s from 7 AGCMs show consistent atmospheric circulation (negative NAM-like) responses to sea-ice variability

Fig 5. DJF SLP EOF1 of SIC-forced interannual variability ($\overline{EXP1 - EXP2}$) from each model. Quadratic trends are removed before EOF calculations. Percentage above panel denotes the explained variance.

5. DJF sea-ice forcing and impacts on surface air temperature, precipitation, stormtrack activity, & blocking

Fig 6. WACCM6 SIC, SAT, precipitation (rainfall + snowfall), 850-hPa stormtrack activity ($\overline{v'v'}$), and 500-hPa blocking regressed onto PC1 of SIC-forced SLP interannual variability. Stippling indicates significance at 5%. Contour lines denote the DJF SLP regressed onto the PC1.

6. Summary

- ~6% of the total SLP variability in the polar cap region (>65°N) is explained by the SIC-forced component in WACCM6 and IPSL-CM6 with 30 members, whereas ~10-20% in other AGCMs with fewer members.
- The variance decomposition analysis suggests at least 30 ensemble members are needed to effectively separate the SIC-forced atmospheric circulation variability from the internal atmospheric noise and SST-GHG forced variability.
- EOF analysis indicates SIC-forced leading mode projects onto negative NAM-like pattern that favors a colder, drier, and more blocked atmospheric conditions in northern Eurasia in response to more sea-ice over the Barents-Kara and Greenland Seas.
- The Arctic SIC increase-Eurasia high pattern relationship in interannual variability is different from the SIC decrease-Eurasia high pattern associated with the long-term trend.